

Geographical analysis of schedule tribe population in Parbhani district- Maharashtra

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Abstract

Present research paper has attempt to study population distribution, growth, density, literacy and sex ratio in tribal population of Parbhani district of Maharashtra state. Geographical distribution of the tribal population was affected by several special factors. Secondary source light census data has been used for analysis from 2001 to 2011. Spatio temporal growth of tribal population has been studied, population has Population has rapidly increased during period under study. it is observed that sex ratio of tribal population improved form 965 in 2001 to 970 in 2011 census. It is also observed that literacy rate in this society increasing slowly. still there was wide disparity in tribal and non-tribal literacy. Literacy rate also defer in male and female. Population structure helps us to solve several types of planning problems like malnutrition and power in this tribe will be reduced with increasing literacy and which become key to unlocking modern society.

Keywords: Sex ratio, Growth of population, Density, Literacy rate

Introduction:

India is the second largest country in the world having a tribal population after Africa. the oldest civilization of tribal society having Ancient History before 5000 to 6000 BC. These tribes retreated after the invasion of Indo Aryan, Dravidian and Mongols from Northwest, South and north-east respectively. In Parbhani district tribal groups reside in valleys, hillslopes, mountains and forests for their protection and habitat. Living in complete harmony with nature, they acquire unique knowledge about the use of natural resources (Chanana 1993) Despite India's recent economic growth, health and Human Development indicated Scheduled Tribes or Adivasi (India's indigenous population) lag behind national averages (Salunke,2013, 2015, 2016, 2018,2019). the aim of this review was to identify the public health interventions for components of these interventions that are effective in reducing morbidity or mortality rates and reducing risks of ill health among ST population in India, in order

inform to policy and to Identify important research gap.

Study area:

Parbhani district located in the central part of Marathwada region is selected for present study. It lies in Godavari River basin. It extends from 18° 45' North latitude to 20° 03' North latitude and 76° 12' East longitude 77° 29' East longitudes. The study region is bounded to the North by Buldhana and Hingoli district, west by Jalna, south by Beed and Latur and east by Nanded. It covers an area of 6511 KM² and has a total population of 1836086 as per the census 2011. It is divided into 09 administrations. These are Parbhani, Selu, Jintur, Manwath, Pathri, Sonpeth, Gangakhed, Palam and Purna. The Hills on the north east form part of the Ajanta Hill ranges which passes through Jintur tahsil. The hills on the southern side are the Balaghat hill ranges in Gangakhed tehsil. The district is at an average height of 457 meter from mean sea level.

Location map of Parbhani District

Objectives: The main objectives of the present research paper are as follow.

1. The study demographic characteristics like growth rate, sex ratio, literacy level, urban rural composition of tribal and non-tribal population in Parbhani district.
2. The compare all aspects with the National and state level average in reference to the 2001 and 2011 census.

Data and methodology

The study is based on purely secondary data like census 2001 to 2011 and some important data Collected from Parbhani district gazetteer and social economic abstract. Information related tribal population and some and some data is collected from Tribal Research & Training Institute (TRTI) Pune. Comparative study of all features done with the help of temporal aspect with the help of temporal aspect. For the analysis of data simple indices like population growth rate, population distribution, male female ratio, Literacy rate, urbanization was used.

We systematically searched and assessed peer reviewed literature on evaluations or intervention studies of a population health intervention undertaken with an ST population or in a tribal area

with a population health outcome and involving primary data collection.

Distribution of schedule tribe in Parbhani district:

A tribe lives separately and occupies a definite and common topography without which it cannot maintain their characteristics like dialect, tradition, culture of community changes the tribe live in inaccessible areas like hilltops, river valleys, forest etc. Physical environment of Jintur Tahsil is adaptable for these tribes because include thick forest cover, river valley of Purna its tributaries, Ajanta range such hill valley topography is favorable for tribal habitat and therefore Jintur tahsil constitute 5% tribal population in district. On the other hand, Selu (1.11), Sonpeth (1.12), Manwath (1.13), Pathri (1.71) Shows very less percentage of tribal people. It is because of sparse vegetation cover, options of Hill Valley topography and natural resources. If one considers the social attachment of tribal people, they are more shy in nature. They never wish to come into contact with modern society. Tehsil road connectivity is high and accessibility is more and it is common hypothesis that concentration of tribals is inversely proportional to the village accessibility and road connectivity.

Table No. 01: Distribution of schedule tribe in Parbhani district-2001 to 2011

Sr. no.	Tehsils	Total population	Total population	Tribal population	Tribal population	% of tribal population	% of tribal population
		2001	2011	2001	2011	2001	2011
1	Sailu	139352	169174	1547	2031	1.11	1.20
2	Jintur	234405	282756	12088	15816	5.16	5.59
3	Parbhani	460778	5378 10	67638	7348	1.46	1.37
4	Manwath	97024	116817	1097	1427	1.13	1.22
5	Pathri	110218	139046	1889	1634	1.71	1.18
6	Sonpeth	66748	89582	747	1005	1.12	1.12
7	Gangakhed	164080	202867	4987	4333	3.04	2.14
8	Palam	92804	115382	3178	4335	3.42	3.76
9	Purna	162306	182652	2939	2585	1.81	1.42
Parbhani district		1527715	1836086	35210	40514	2.30	2.21

Source: 2001 and 2011 census report

Population growth:

Total population of the district recorded 2117035 in 1901 and a decrease of population 1527715 in 2001. Because in this period jurisdictional changes included carving out of the new district Hingoli out of Parbhani district on 1st May 1999. The population increased by fivefold within a period of a century. Except for the 1921 Census, all

enumeration shows positive growth in population growth rate in the decade 1991-2001 increased rapidly in certain areas of Parbhani (+0.43) tehsil. On other hand Pathri (-50.95) Shows negative growth of population. Sach impact may happen due to the formation of Manwath and Selu as a new Tahsil and Gangakhed (-36.67) shows Negative growth of population. Such impact may happen due

to formation of Palam, Purna and Sonpeth as a new three tehsil.

Table No. 02: Growth of tribe population in Parbhani district-2001 to 2011

Sr. no.	Tehsils	1991 Tribal population	2001 Tribal population	1991-2001 Growth rate	2001 Tribal population	2011 Tribal population	2001-2011 Growth rate
1	Sailu	--	1547	--	1547	2031	+31.29
2	Jintur	12349	12088	-2.11	12088	15816	+30.84
3	Parbhani	6709	6738	+0.43	6738	7348	+9.05
4	Manwath	--	1097	--	1097	1427	+30.08
5	Pathri	3851	1889	-50.95	1889	1634	-13.50
6	Sonpeth	--	747	--	747	1005	+34.54
7	Gangakhed	7875	4987	-36.67	4987	4333	-13.11
8	Palam	--	3178	--	3178	4335	+36.41
9	Purna	--	2939	--	2939	2585	-12.05
Parbhani district		30784	35210	+14.38	35210	40514	+15.06

Source: 1991, 2001 and 2011 census report

Sex ratio:

Sex ratio is considered as one of the best indicators of social, economic and culture development. Sex ratio always express the social set up of society set up of society. One of the most striking features of tribal society is that they show a high proportion of females in comparison to non-tribals. In general scenario Manwath (982) females per 1000 males. It is due to its unfavorable physical set up and huge migration towards Mumbai, Pune and major industrial sector in search of employment on contract Parbhani tehsil depict lowest sex ratio (945/1000 males) due to MIDC and Parbhani city created more job opportunities in tehsil and its destination point of several migrants. This type of migration is male selective so such effect of low and

high sex ratio come into exist. It is noticeable that sex ratio come into exit. It is noticeable that sex ratio in tribal region remain always high in comparison of non-tribal society. Palam (1008), Sailu (994) shows quite good sex ration the other hand Gangakhed (917) Pathri (924) prove less number of females some tehsils like Jintur and Parbhani are exception to this rule. Generally tribal area indicates high sex ratio because in tribal community female is equally important as male in certain tribal group mother dominating society exists therefore number of women is quite high in tribes. Girls help their mother in housework before the marriage bride receives dowry. All these reasons are responsible for high sex ratio in tribe.

Table No. 03: Sex Ratio in tribals

Sr. no.	Tehsils	Sex Ratio of total population	Sex Ratio of Tribal population	Sex Ratio of total population	Sex Ratio of Tribal population
		2001	2001	2011	2011
1	Sailu	968	994	953	978
2	Jintur	966	973	952	978
3	Parbhani	945	971	954	973
4	Manwath	982	947	955	963
5	Pathri	964	924	945	943
6	Sonpeth	974	940	937	1022

7	Gangakhed	949	917	935	934
8	Palam	956	1008	931	966
9	Purna	951	931	943	973
Parbhani district		957	965	947	970

Source: 2001 and 2011 census report

Conclusion:

The above discussion of demographic aspect of scheduled tribe population in Parbhani district. The discussion and result it is clear that Scheduled tribe in this district in transition zone. It is pathetic that after 62 years of independence tribal are facing same situation. Several schemes penetrate due to corruption and development remains for only name and fame. But situation is changing by slowly sex ratio of this tribal community always more than modern society. Urbanization in tribal is quite slow but still is moving by progress is observe in literacy rate and educational attainment. Population structure help us for several type of planning misery and poverty in this tribe will reduce with increasing literacy and which become key of unlocked modern society.

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